

FORMATION OF BASIC ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN STUDENTS BASED ON LEARNING OUTCOMES AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS

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Abstract. *The formation of entrepreneurial skills in students based on learning outcomes is one of the important areas, which serves to train personnel suitable for the country's economy, ensure the employment of young people in the form of entrepreneurship, and develop qualified specialists in society. The political and legal framework for directing students to entrepreneurship is often determined by laws and regulatory documents. These documents cover the requirements for entrepreneurial education, the rights of young people to acquire skills, and support provided to students by the state. In our country, international programs on determining the literacy and competence of students and monitoring the quality of education provide for improving the quality of teaching in specific subjects, improving their theoretical, methodological and methodological foundations, and assessing the level of independent knowledge acquisition as a separate parameter. The reforms being implemented in the context of active innovation processes in the social and economic spheres of our society have put on the agenda one of the main trends in the development of the education system - the problem of developing entrepreneurial intellectual qualities in students in vocational and technical schools.*

Keywords: *talent, intellectual, entrepreneurship, competitiveness, education, labor market, profession, startup.*

Introduction. The career guidance of students is one of the important directions of the education system, serving to produce qualified specialists that meet the needs of the national economy, ensuring youth employment, and contributing to the emergence of skilled professionals in society. The political and legal framework for guiding students towards careers is often defined by laws and regulatory documents. These documents encompass the requirements for vocational education, the rights of young people to find employment, and the support provided by the state to students. In our country, efforts are made to assess the literacy and competencies of students, to enhance the quality of teaching through the study of international programs, and to improve the theoretical, methodological, and instructional foundations, as well as to evaluate independent knowledge acquisition levels as a separate parameter. In the context of innovative processes in the social and economic spheres of our society, the ongoing reforms are one of the main trends in the development of the education system, highlighting the issue of developing the intellectual qualities of students in academic lyceums as a priority on the agenda.

Guiding students towards entrepreneurship is very necessary in today's rapidly changing labor market, taking into account the interests and abilities of students and guiding them to choose the right entrepreneurial skills. This process plays an important role not only in determining the future of students, but also in the development of our economy. Today, in creating the foundation for development and the future, choosing entrepreneurial skills and which direction to take is an

important step, and the main thing is to increase mental potential. When choosing an entrepreneurial direction, it is important for students to be provided with the necessary information and skills, to study foreign and domestic literature and practical processes, as well as their personal interests and talents. Such an approach serves to educate a generation of future successful specialists and to give them an intellectual and realistic outlook on life.

Existing problems in the industry. When working on the formation of entrepreneurial skills in educational organizations, vocational schools, colleges and technical schools, the following factors are taken into account in the targeted training programs for gifted students, which are important for them to master:

- high level of mastery in the field of entrepreneurship and other disciplines;
- computer literacy and in-depth knowledge of programming;
- foreign language literacy;
- acquire the skills and competencies to think independently and express new ideas in the process of performing scientific and creative work;
- quickly master new innovations in the industry;
- accurate calculations and the ability to foresee the future and acquire knowledge about new approaches;
- to present oneself as a patriotic, well-rounded person who correctly understands and supports the state's strategy, domestic and foreign policies.

It is known that the creation of the necessary conditions for the upbringing and education of gifted students contributes to the formation of a national elite in different countries, ensures the achievements of science, art and the competitiveness of the national economy. The manifestation of this talent is necessary not only for the individual, but also for society and its development. The importance of this most important strategic national task encourages a deeper study of the theoretical (concepts, types, forms of manifestation, etc.) and practical aspects (organizational forms of working with gifted children) of children's talent. Talent is the potential of the psyche, which systematically develops throughout the life of the human psyche, ensuring the achievement of non-traditional and extraordinary results in relation to others. Talent directs all human capabilities and thinking to solve new life challenges and adapt to new innovative conditions. The problems of searching for, selecting and demonstrating talents, teaching and educating them remain relevant for scientists and practitioners around the world.

A sufficient amount of material has been accumulated in the study of gifted children of different ages, which encourages us to think about the connection of these or those age characteristics with the sparks of talent, that is, their integration, and the course of age changes. According to the American Psychologist L. Terman, “proper upbringing of gifted children” will lead to their becoming “ideal adults” and their achieving success in real life. Therefore, the formation and preservation of children's talents and entrepreneurial skills is a pedagogical problem, and in fact, an educational problem. Many researchers have come to the conclusion that most gifted children have special features that distinguish them from many of their peers. Working on oneself and understanding the entrepreneurial skills and essence of new projects, the ways of knowing the world in gifted children do not always correspond to the traditional educational environment. Because for gifted children, understanding this world is one of the usual phenomena that organically fit into their perception. Today, a number of problems arise in guiding students towards entrepreneurship.

As a result, there is a shortage of specialists in the areas entering the labor market, and it is necessary to attract specialists from abroad. If we do not find a comprehensive solution to this problem, this problem will take root and in the future very large gaps may appear. First, there are misunderstandings due to parental interference in the direction of the educational organization in the formation of active entrepreneurial skills for its students who will enter the labor market in the future. The main issue in the formation of legal and entrepreneurial skills in the current generation is awareness of the legislation and the last 8 years of being aware of the state's benefits for entrepreneurs. The main goal is to develop entrepreneurial skills in young people in practice and to harmonize lessons, as a result of which the formation of entrepreneurial skills in them will be the main criterion. Young people face social and family pressures in the formation of entrepreneurial skills and in choosing a specific direction. It is the demands of the family and those around them that force young people to choose entrepreneurship contrary to their own desires. This leads to stress for young people and choosing entrepreneurship that does not match their abilities. Secondly, in educational institutions and families, students are not provided with information about the new 21st-22nd century entrepreneurial skills. Unfortunately, parents are in favor of their children becoming owners of popular areas such as medicine, banking, economics, prosecutor's office, internal affairs, law, and teaching. However, in the next 9 years, parents are not aware of the increasing demand for GMO agronomists, blockchain systems specialists, cybersecurity administrators, cyberprostheses and implants developers, marketers, bioengineers, telemedicine, 3D designers, VR programmers, artificial intelligence engineers, drone operators, and modern entrepreneurship in these and other areas.

Thirdly, it is also common in practice that psychologists in educational institutions and consultants in specialized educational institutions do not properly organize outreach work with students on future entrepreneurial skills. Fourthly, there are artificial barriers to women and men working in the fields based on gender stereotypes. Experience shows that in the Uzbek mentality, some areas of entrepreneurship are designated for women, and others for men. This is reflected in families where fathers or mothers force daughters to choose a narrow range of areas in the formation and selection of entrepreneurial skills. In education, it has also been observed that more boys choose the exact sciences and more girls choose the natural sciences. As clear evidence of this, it was revealed that there are imbalances when analyzing students studying in the exact and natural sciences in the system of the Agency for Specialized Educational Institutions in the 2024-2025 academic year.

Small business and private entrepreneurship have been identified as priority areas of our country's economy. Over the past seven years, about 2.1 thousand laws, decrees and resolutions have been adopted aimed at developing this sector. 116 licenses and permits for entrepreneurial activity have been canceled, a notification procedure has been introduced for 34 types of activity. The procedures for obtaining permits have been simplified and the terms for their issuance have been reduced by an average of 2.2 times. Unnecessary inspections have been canceled, restrictions on the circulation of cash, currency and raw materials have been lifted. As a result of such opportunities, the number of new business entities is rapidly increasing, and the activities of existing ones are expanding. Over the past five years, the number of entrepreneurs has almost tripled. Many businessmen have expanded their businesses throughout the country, created thousands of jobs, and become large, successful companies. A class of entrepreneurs with their own brand in the domestic and foreign markets has begun to form.

1. Advanced foreign experience in this field

Problems in the formation and orientation of students' entrepreneurial skills and advanced foreign experiences in solving them. The formation and orientation of students' entrepreneurial skills plays an important role in the integration of the education system and the labor market. In world experience, there are various models and approaches to effectively implementing this process. Taking into account the existing problems in Uzbekistan, it is advisable to study and implement the following advanced foreign experiences.

1. German experience: In Germany, a “dual education system” has been introduced, which ensures that students simultaneously receive education and participate in the production process. 71% of training is aimed at internships in enterprises and organizations. Enterprises participating in the training process are obliged to provide employment to young specialists, and employers are directly involved in the development of training programs to develop entrepreneurial skills.

2. Finnish experience. In Finland, “career counselors” operate in every school and guide students according to their personal interests, students are advised on the formation of entrepreneurial skills from the moment they enter education, educational organizations and centers work together, preparing students for real labor market conditions. This experience is now being introduced in colleges, lyceums, and technical schools in the system, and practical work is being carried out in this area.

3. Japanese experience, Japanese educational institutions pay great attention to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics), entrepreneurship education is focused on areas such as robotics, artificial intelligence, and programming. Advanced technologies and interactive methods are used in the learning process.

4. US experience - increasing private sector participation in entrepreneurship orientation In the US, the participation of the private sector in the development of education in the formation of entrepreneurial skills is important, large manufacturing companies provide grants to technical schools and vocational colleges. Agreements are concluded between enterprises and educational institutions, and graduates are provided with guaranteed jobs.

2. Proposals for solving these problems The following proposals can be put forward to solve the above problems. The following are proposed as solutions: It is advisable to introduce an educational organization consultant responsible for guiding students in the formation of entrepreneurial skills in these educational organizations, where there are colleges, vocational schools, and technical schools in almost every district or city. It would be advisable for the consultants of this educational organization to carry out promotional work in each educational organization or neighborhood, in collaboration with activists, on the formation of new entrepreneurial skills that will enter the labor market in the future. The demand for labor resources in the global market is changing dramatically. Currently, the need for specialists in such areas as robotics, artificial intelligence, biotechnology, digital marketing, and creative industries is increasing. Therefore, targeted training of young people in these areas is of great importance. Fundamental measures must be taken to ensure that the Uzbek education system adapts to these changes.

Suggestions:

Firstly, redeveloping vocational education standards to include the skills necessary for 21st-22nd century professions and entrepreneurship (soft skills, critical thinking, data analytics, creativity, entrepreneurship, IT) in the curriculum, introducing the subject “21st-22nd century skills” in schools. Widely using the Project-Based Learning method in educational processes. Secondly, organizing practical training on digital literacy, cybersecurity and artificial intelligence.

Thirdly, strengthening cooperation between employers and educational institutions. Developing specialized programs in collaboration with enterprises. Integrating the business and startup ecosystem with education. Fourthly, it would be appropriate to create opportunities for dual education and cooperation with production so that 52% of college, technical school, vocational and university students spend practical training in production. Fifth, expand Internship and Apprenticeship Programs Make it mandatory for every student to have at least one internship. Organize events such as the “Start-up Challenge” for young people in collaboration with startups and business incubators. Sixth, increase attention to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) education by introducing IT, artificial intelligence, robotics, cybersecurity, and data analysis courses in schools. Organize programs such as “Coding for Kids” and “AI for Beginners.” Establish research laboratories at universities. Expand grant programs for young engineers and researchers. Seventh, develop “EdTech” (Educational Technology) platforms Develop online education courses for students. Create personalized learning platforms using artificial intelligence to develop distance learning.

Conclusion. The formation and orientation of students in entrepreneurial skills is one of the important directions of the education system, which serves to train personnel suitable for the country's economy, ensure youth employment, and produce qualified specialists in society. The demand for labor resources in the global market is changing dramatically. Currently, the need for specialists in such areas as robotics, artificial intelligence, biotechnology, digital marketing, and creative industries is increasing.

In the current modern era, the main issue in the formation of legal and entrepreneurial skills is awareness of the legislation and the state's incentives for entrepreneurs. The main goal is to develop entrepreneurial skills in young people in practice and conduct classes together, which will be the main criterion for the formation of basic entrepreneurial skills in them.

Therefore, targeted training of young people in these areas is of great importance. Fundamental measures must be taken to ensure that the education system of Uzbekistan adapts to these changes. The formation of entrepreneurial skills is one of the most important decisions that affects the future of each person. The role of parents in this process is of great importance, because they are the first mentors and guides for their children.

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